

NEW APPROACHES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Jalilova Xolidaxon Fayzullo qizi

Independent researcher

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ABSTRACT

This article presents some information about new approaches of teaching foreign languages. It has also discusses about different methods of teaching and learning foreign languages.

In today's rapidly developing era, the demand for knowledge of foreign languages, acquisition of skills and further expansion of the knowledge of industry workers greatly increases the need to learn languages. The use of information technologies and modern methods and various methods in teaching, creative approaches of pedagogues in the field of education effectively help in quick and easy learning of the language. It becomes easier for the student to master a certain educational program by choosing the method which suits him from among various methods. Therefore, pedagogues and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the skills of choosing the most effective ways of learning are formed. Teaching and collecting information on this language with them based on transportation and checking of the student's existing knowledge. As time progresses day by day, news in the field is increasing.

Nowadays, improving the quality and efficiency of education is an important stage for the development of industries and our development. It is not interesting for today's advanced youth to sit in boring classrooms, listen to long rules of language learning and see examples in pictures. After all, in a world of distractions, there are enough factors that attract the reader, for example, we can take as an example low-quality videos that waste time on various social networks.

Nowadays, it is more interesting for young people to learn languages in modern and creatively equipped auditoriums (with a linguaphone, a maximum monitor for videos and a sound amplifier). Based on the student's request, teacher should encourage the rational and correct use of social networks in language learning, and motivate the student to learn the language outside the classroom. Currently, pedagogues widely use mnemonic methods in education, which is the most effective solution.

Although the use of mnemonics in education has only recently entered our country, it is a field that has been used in European countries for a long time, and its effectiveness has been confirmed. Mnemonics (from the Greek mnemonics - the art of remembering) is a system of methods that facilitate remembering and expand memory by creating artificial associations. Learning the language students use ineffective materials because they are used to using various artificial methods. But the method that increases the efficiency of memory in a fundamental sense is memorizing these words by connecting them with imagination. The most important thing in mnemonics is imagination and the ability to associate it with the words we want to remember. Let's look at examples of the most effective and popular methods. In the essence of "Loki" and "Mountain" methods, great importance is attached to remembering by imagination.

Loki's method: Loki - recall through locations. That is, in this method, when remembering words or texts, we use objects from a well-known place (our home, auditorium, workplace). For example, the words we want to memorize: magic, hero, castle, we want to remember them using the "Loki" method. For this, we remember the location of a place known to us, for example, the audience. Starting from the entrance door, we can select 3 objects as location, for example door, monitor, window. Now we can place these words in our three locations and create an image. We put magic on our door and connect it to each other. Imagine the door is magical, its colors are amazing, smoke comes out around it, the shapes change in different ways. We pronounce magic-sehir out loud. Now let's look at the next word and object, monitor and the word hero. Imagine the hero Hulk is explaining a lesson on the monitor. Pronounce it hero-qahramon. Last word and object castle -saroy and window - deraza. The ends of the tower of the castle visible from the window have been cut off. Pronounce castle. Now we will pronounce the words in each of our locations. Through imagination, words remain in the memory for a long time. **"Tog" method:** Tog is also a widely used method for memorizing foreign words in mnemonics.

G-harmonization This method consists of 3 main elements: translation, image, we translate the word of harmonization and find an image associated with this word. **"Tomato" method:** Through this method, the student learns a language while following time management. This method also helps to get rid of laziness. Because it is easy for a person to get distracted while doing some heavy mental work. This method is widely used to solve the same problem. **Tomato method:** set the timer for 25 minutes, exercise for 5 minutes, exercise for another 25 minutes, rest for 5 minutes, repeat this 5-6 times, then rest for 1-2 hours. For example, we have to memorize 120 words in 3 hours. If we divide it by time, we will have to memorize 40 words per hour. This means that we need to use 6 tomatoes. 1st hour: 25 minutes 20 words - 5 minutes rest, 25 minutes 20 words - 5 minutes rest, 2nd hour: 25 minutes 20 words - 5 minutes rest, 25 minutes 20 words - 5 minutes of rest, 3rd hour: 25 minutes 20 words - 5 minutes of rest, 25 minutes 20 words - 5 minutes of rest, After we finish, we rest and make 2 more tomatoes 60 repetitions of all memorized words, we repeat 120 words. It is through this method that students practice time management they learn foreign languages quickly by memorizing words. Our article was written not only for language learners but also for teachers. In the developing century, when learning a science, including

learning foreign languages, first of all, a teacher should be in tune with the times. We learn new approaches from qualified teachers who work on themselves.

Several theories and approaches have emerged over the years to study and analyze the process of language acquisition. The main schools of thought, which provide theoretical paradigms in guiding the course of language acquisition are, innatist theory, cognitive theory, motherese theory, behaviourism, merged theory. The Innate theory asserts that language is an innate capacity and that a child's brain contains special language-learning mechanisms at birth in which the main proponent of this theory is Chomsky. On the other hand, the cognitive theory by Jean Piaget claims that language is just one aspect of a child's overall intellectual development. Sassonian asserts that language is a symbolic representation which allows the children to abstract the world.

Child-centered "Motherese" is universal, and there are cultures in which speech is never addressed to language-learning children. More so, the essay will critically discuss the cognitive theory and also the Chomsky innateness theory of children having innate ideas to learn language and also how this language acquisition is learned and developed by social interacting with environments such as adults and the cognitive development. Also, I will be highlighting studies that have critiqued Motherese and the other theories of not being helpful to children in acquiring language [1].

Language is not an autonomous system for communication. It is embedded in and supplemented by gesture, gaze, stance, facial expression, voice quality in the full array of options people can use for communicating. Learning is complex and the context where it takes place is influenced by our learning experience due to our different experiences. Clark states that "in learning language, children may first rely on nonlinguistic options, both in their initial understanding and in their own early use".

However, in literatures, some scholars have argued and critiqued the innateness of language as it relates to having nothing defending the thesis. Sampson argues that to say that language is not innate is to say that there is no difference between my granddaughter, a rock and a rabbit. According to Sampson if you take a rock, a rabbit and my granddaughter and put them in a community where people are talking English, they will all learn English. This simply implies that if there is a difference therefore language is not innate. Although Chomsky argues that children learn their first language remarkably fast and also it is relatively fast. In contrast, Sampson argues that people normally reckon the period of language acquisition from birth and children take years from birth, rather than months or weeks to master the main grammatical structures of their mother tongue. Gethin in a similar vein argues that adults who go about it the right way can acquire a far larger vocabulary in a foreign language and far quickly than native child for reason that adults know the world already, while children do not [2].

Meanwhile, Chomsky argues that language acquisition in childhood works quite differently from acquisition in later life and their learning of language is more complicated than the last. Gethin further claims that "it is an unwarranted assumption that children go through stages in this order because one stage is simpler than another; nor does it follow that because a general psychological reason is not observable and there is not one". Sampson refutes this assumption by explaining the best-known case of Genie.

The Input theory

According to the input or Motherese theory, there are cultures in which speech is never addressed to language-learning children; therefore it must be possible to learn to talk by listening to adults talking to each other or by the environments surrounding them. The studies of Motherese in the 1970 focused upon the maternal input, that parents do not talk to their children in the same way as they talk to other adults and seem to be capable and adapting their language to give the child maximum opportunity to interact and learn. This implies that the child moves ahead a little at time. Adults do talk differently to children than to other adults using what is sometimes called “Motherese”. Crain and Lillo-Martin argue that “adults mumble less to children, they use fewer incorrectly formed sentences, they use shorter sentences, and they frequently use different intonation patterns with young children”.

Mothers are able to provide semantically relevant and interpretable speech because they follow up on topics introduced by the child; but some mothers will be better at doing this than others. It also shows that some children will be better at eliciting semantically relevant and interpretable speech than others. The utterance of the parents is considerably and subconsciously simplified especially with respect to grammar and meaning and sentences are shorter. However various studies have indicated that they do not invariably use grammatically simpler sentences. Crain and Lillo-Martin pose that looking at studies that compared children whose parents used Motherese to those whose parents did not use Motherese, no different was found in language development. So it does not seem that Motherese serves to pace the information presented to the child, in order to help her learn the language in easy steps and must be clear that Motherese would not be helpful, and “could be detrimental to language development in certain cases”. Pinker objects to the claims of Crain and Lillo-Martin in his findings and asserts that he has observed the results of the experiment that we do not teach our children to sit, stand, walk, but they do it on their own schedule.

Although, it is clear that the idea of child-centered “Motherese” is universal comes under the behaviorism theory because it is about children who imitate adults that their correct utterances are reinforced when they get what they want or are praised. Behaviorism theory has been criticized by David McNeill that children are unable to imitate adult’s grammatical constructions exactly, thus language acquisition is more of a matter of maturation than of imitation. Also the input theory or Motherese is criticized for its difficulty to show connection between the features of Motherese and the subsequence that arise out of these features in child speech. In essence, it is clear that children spend much of their time listening to conversation around them rather than directly taking part in them.

Psychological level: the feelings of speech partners for each other, their relationship, their mutual expectancies, and the respective levels of maturation, which determine the choice of words by the speaker and the interpretation of their meaning by the listener.

Linguistic level: process of word finding; selecting the correct sounds and putting them into correct sequences; putting words into correct grammatical order to form sentences.

Physiological level: Neural activities affecting the speaker’s perceptual and motor mechanisms and activating the hearing mechanisms of speakers and listener.

Acoustic level: Sound waves travelling through the air between speaker and listener. There is not much evidence of the effects of the presence of siblings on children’s language. On

the other hand, Lieven reviews a report on young children's language in conversations which include their mother and an older sibling as more complex than when alone with the mother.

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